

Analysis of the Family of Hope Program in Protecting the Homeless to Create a Welfare State

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of the study is to analyze the Family Hope (PKH) program in protecting the homeless in order to raise the level of the homeless economy from the perspective of the welfare state. PKH is a conditional cash direct funding program implemented by the Ministry of Social Affairs to improve public welfare, especially in the education and health sectors. The research method used is literature research, through the collection of information from various reliable sources related to PKH and the concept of the welfare state. The results of the analysis show that PKH can be considered as an approach to social protection of the homeless in the context of the welfare state. PKH aims to reduce poverty and improve quality of life through access to education. To improve the effectiveness of PKH, it is necessary to strengthen cooperation between agencies such as the Ministry of Social Affairs, Ministry of Health and Ministry of Education and culture. The legal basis used is Law No. 11 of 2009 on social welfare, Article 33 of the 1945 Constitution after amendment, and Menkokesra decision, namely: No. 031/KEP/MENKO/-KESRA/IX/2007 in addition, good coordination between Related Agencies will help optimize available resources and minimize obstacles in the implementation of social welfare programs. In addition, it is also important to improve the monitoring system and periodic evaluation of the implementation of PKH, in order to ensure that the program is carried out, according to the desired goals and provide optimal benefits to the community.

INTRODUCTION

Basically, every country must have responsibilities, duties and goals to be achieved. The goals of each country will be different from each other because they are influenced by social values, geographical conditions, the history of its formation and the political influence of that country. Law Number 11 of 2009 concerning Social Welfare is proof that welfare is so important for this country that it must be regulated in a law so that the intended welfare can be achieved for the common good, in fact welfare does not only talk about how the state is responsible to its people but This welfare is also a measure of success for a country. However, the challenges faced by Indonesia in achieving people's welfare are quite difficult because Indonesia has a large territory and a large population spread across its territory.

To overcome this welfare problem, the Government in 2007 launched a program called the Family Hope Program, this program is a conditional cash assistance program given to the Very Poor Family category which has several conditions including related to education and health. This program is implemented by regions that are deemed to need program assistance and meet several requirements determined by policy makers. The implementation of the Family Hope Program (PKH) is carried out by the directorate that handles PKH implementation at the Ministry of Social Affairs, and regional social services, both provincial and district/city, which handle PKH Social Assistance, protection and social security in the regions.

The Family Hope Program, which was later abbreviated as PKH, aims to improve human quality through providing conditional direct cash assistance to underprivileged families so they can enjoy health and education facilities. PKH encourages reducing the burden of household spending on underprivileged families in the form of direct consumption needs as well as investment in health and education in the future so that it has a positive impact on the development of human capabilities. This combination of short and long term assistance is part of the government's strategy to reduce poverty. PKH management is carried out by the Ministry of Social Affairs which is supervised by Bappenas. The first implementation of this policy had slow progress. This can be observed through the limited scope of the program and the provisions on the total number of families or regions entitled to receive benefits. In 2010, the Secretariat of the National Team for the Acceleration of Poverty Reduction (TNP2K) stimulated the expansion of the PKH coverage area, thus having a positive impact on more effective and efficient implementation.

In general, the aim of the PKH program is to reduce poverty and improve the quality of human resources in underprivileged communities. However, the implementation of this program still faces several challenges, such as limited program coverage, lack of proper PKH implementation, additional costs in PKH payments, and not all PKH members receive additional programs, especially KIP or KIS. Evaluation of the PKH program in several regions shows that this program is running quite well, but the process of disbursing PKH funds needs to be improved to minimize delays in disbursement of funds. Then, improvements are needed in updating the data, because there are several

people in the well-off category who receive benefits from PKH assistance. Thus, it is necessary to carry out continuous evaluation and improvement in the implementation of the PKH program to ensure that the program can provide maximum benefits to poor families in Indonesia.

LITERATURE REVIEW

PKH also aims to protect homeless people from poverty or as a process of raising the homeless economy from pre-prosperous to prosperous stage. Homeless people are a group of people who are very vulnerable to poverty and difficulty in meeting basic needs. PKH provides assistance to very poor families, including homeless groups, to help them meet their basic needs and improve their quality of life. Therefore, it is important to analyze the effectiveness of PKH in protecting homelessness and ensure that the program can provide maximum benefits to poor families in Indonesia. Continuous evaluation and improvement in the implementation of the PKH program needs to be carried out to ensure that the program can provide maximum benefits for poor families in Indonesia, including homeless groups. Therefore, the identification of the problem is: How effective is PKH in protecting homeless people in Indonesia from a welfare state perspective?

METHODOLOGY

This research uses a normative method with a qualitative descriptive approach. This method is used to describe phenomena or events that occur in detail and in depth. This research was carried out by collecting data from various sources, such as documents, reports and previous research results. In conducting this research, researchers can use several indicators to measure the effectiveness of the Family Hope Program in protecting homeless people, such as the number of homeless people registered as PKH beneficiaries, the level of homeless participation in the PKH program, and the impact of the PKH program on the welfare of homeless people. Researchers also analyzed the perspective of the welfare state in implementing the PKH program, taking into account aspects such as public policy, human rights and social justice.

RESULTS AND DISSCUSION

A. Welfare State: Understanding and Foundations of the Family Hope Program

1. Welfare State Concept

A welfare state is a state concept where its implementation is based on laws or regulations established by the authorities. However, what is different is that the welfare state is also actively involved in improving the welfare of its people. This concept is also known as verzorgingsstaat or sociale rechtsstaat, which literally means a state that prioritizes social welfare. The development of the welfare state is characterized by the emergence of the government's responsibility in achieving general welfare for its citizens. In this case, the teachings of the welfare state are a concrete manifestation of a paradigm shift, where the role of the state was previously limited to intervening in the socio-

economic life of society, changing to the role of the state being actively involved (*staatsbemoeyenis*) in the socio-economic life of society. This aims to create general welfare, as well as maintaining order and security in society. The material legal state type includes a broader concept than the legal state, which is generally referred to as the modern legal state. In a material law type of country, the government's duties are not limited to implementing the provisions of the law, but also involve making laws or implementing regulations. The state has an obligation to be actively involved in various aspects of its people's lives in order to achieve state goals. The previous concept where the government should not interfere in citizens' affairs has changed so that the government must intervene and be responsible for the welfare of society.

The main key in a welfare state is the issue of guaranteeing the welfare of the people by the state. Regarding this matter, Jurgen Habermas is of the opinion that guaranteeing the welfare of all people is the main thing for a modern state. Furthermore, according to Habermas, the guarantee of the welfare of all the people in question is realized in the protection of the risk of unemployment, accident, illness, old age, and death of the breadwinner must be covered to a large extent through welfare provisions of the state. The Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia also adheres to the ideology of the Welfare State. This was emphasized by the Pioneers of Independence and the Founders of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia that the democratic state to be established was a "Welfare State" (*walvaarstaat*) not a "Night Watchman State" (*nachtwachterstaat*). In this choice regarding the conception of the Indonesian welfare state, Moh. Hatta used the term "Administrative State".

In the 1945 Constitution, social welfare is a special title for Chapter This means that social welfare is actually a platform for the economic system and social system in Indonesia. So, in fact, Indonesia is a country that adheres to the ideology of the "welfare state" with the "participatory welfare state" model, which in social work literature is known as welfare pluralism. This model emphasizes that the state must remain take part in handling social problems and implementing social security, although its operationalization still involves the community.

Based on Article 33 of the 1945 Constitution, after the amendment, Indonesia is a country with a welfare state, not a country with liberal views. Because the 1945 Constitution does not only contain political sovereignty, but also regulates social and economic structures. This is different from liberal countries whose constitutions do not contain regulations on social and economic structures but only contain political sovereignty. This means that the welfare state model based on the 1945 Constitution describes the very large role of the state in regulating the economy, redistributing economic justice and democratizing the economic system on a family and joint venture model under state control. The government must be active in creating socio-economic prosperity in society. Democracy in this new context must be understood broadly, this includes the economic dimension with a set of systems that are able to control the economy, reduce socio-economic disparities, especially when

overcoming the unequal distribution of wealth in society. This idea later created the concept of the welfare state.

2. Implementation and Foundation of the Family Hope Program

The PKH program is a social assistance program for underprivileged families who are registered with the Poverty Handling Program on a conditional basis, where on the basis of this data they are then determined to be families who are beneficiaries of PKH. PKH is organized by the Ministry of Social Affairs with the aim of improving community welfare, especially in the education and health sectors. The aim of PKH is to improve the quality of life of "Very Poor Households (RTSM)" which is focused on access to the health and education sectors that have been determined. In its implementation, PKH is supervised by the National Development Planning Agency (Bappenas) and managed by the Ministry of Social Affairs (Kemensos). PKH implementation is carried out by providing cash assistance to poor families, in this case homeless or homeless people are included in this category. This cash assistance is generally given with the following conditions: First, be an Indonesian citizen (WNI), Second, have an identity card (E-KTP), Third, not be a government employee or state civil servant (ASN), Fourth, be included in the criteria for the poor or vulnerable to poverty, This is proven by the amount of income or certain opinions generated within a period of at least one month. Fifth, be registered or recorded in the integrated social welfare data (DTKS) by registering via the website cekbansos.kemensos.go.id. PKH is also implemented by forming groups of PKH participants and verifying the commitment of PKH participants. The implementation of PKH also involves PKH assistants who are tasked with assisting PKH beneficiary families in accessing health and education services. The foundation of PKH is the Decree of the Minister of Social Affairs, namely: Number 031/KEP/MENKO/-KESRA/IX/2007 concerning the "Family Hope Program Control Team." PKH is also supported by the Secretariat of the National Team for the Acceleration of Poverty Reduction (TNP2K) with the hope of encouraging the expansion of PKH coverage and the implementation of programs that are more efficient and have a positive impact on the poor, including the homeless, and to avoid "misdirected aid", both in the form of families. It is no longer included in the categories of vulnerable poor or destitute and people who are capable but are registered as recipients of PKH cash assistance.

B. Understanding the Effectiveness of PKH as an Approach to Handling Homelessness from a Welfare State Perspective

The welfare state is a reflection of the legal system. Thus, all state activities need to be based on law. In his legal perspective, Wilhelm Linstedt stated: "Law is nothing but the very life of mindkind in organized groups and the condition which makes possible peaceful co-existence of masses of individuals and social groups and the corporation for other ends than mere existence and propagation. " The material law state is generally also called the "Welfare State" which emphasizes the welfare of its population.

Indonesia is one of several countries that has adopted the concept of "Welfare State". This was emphasized by the pioneers of independence, namely that Indonesia is a democratic country with the concept of a "Welfare State". In the context of the choice regarding adopting the concept of "Welfare State", Moh Hatta referred to it as "Administrative State". The principle of "Welfare State" in the 1945 Constitution can be found in several articles, especially those related to socio-economics. The travel goals of world governments are of course based on noble goals and ideals. Likewise, Indonesia firmly "protects the entire Indonesian nation, promotes general welfare, makes the nation's life intelligent, and plays a role in maintaining world order based on independence, eternal peace and social justice."

In the reality of the Welfare State, its manifestation is a reflection of the results of human desires to obtain a sense of security, tranquility and prosperity that guarantees them to avoid misery. This reason is the driving force and goal of humans to always try to achieve prosperity in their lives. If this desire is guaranteed by the constitution, then the state is obliged to guarantee and make it happen. In this context, the state plays the role of a welfare state. With the inclusion of welfare aspects in the 1945 Constitution, Jimly As-Shidiqie said that the Indonesian constitution could be called a social and economic constitution. This is in accordance with the constitutions of several countries, namely "Russia, Bulgaria, Czechoslovakia, Albania, Italy, Belarus, Iran, Syria and Hungary." Jimly also said that the 1945 Constitution was influenced by the constitutional writing style commonly found in socialist countries.

The concept of social welfare in the 1945 Constitution is reflected in Article 33 concerning the Economic System, Article 34 concerning "State Attention to Vulnerable Groups (Poor Poor and Abandoned Children), and the Social Security System." The existence of social welfare is basically the basis of the economic system and social system in Indonesia. Indonesia adheres to the concept of a "Welfare State" modeled on a welfare state. The 1945 Constitution explains the articles related to the welfare state, namely:

- a. Article 34 which reads: The poor and neglected children are cared for by the state. This article very clearly describes the state's obligation to care for the poor and neglected children.
- b. Article 28H paragraph 3 reads: Every person has the right to social security which enables his/her full development as a dignified human being. In this article, the role of central and regional governments must be to facilitate every individual to develop their potential so that they can live their lives well.
- c. Article 27 paragraph 2 reads: Every citizen has the right to work and a living worthy of humanity. In this article, the government and every citizen are obliged to do something a to achieve prosperity. Because if it is only carried out by one party, there will be no significant changes.

The principles of the welfare state concept are equality of opportunity, equal distribution of wealth, and public responsibility for those who are unable to provide themselves with the minimum needs to live a decent life. The essence of the welfare state concept is the state's responsibility for the welfare of its citizens, where the government plays a key role in protecting and improving the economic and social welfare of its citizens.

The welfare state is a concept where the state is responsible for ensuring social welfare for all its citizens. One form of state responsibility in protecting social welfare is through social assistance programs. The Family Hope Program (PKH) is an example of a social assistance program carried out in the context of a welfare state. PKH is a program that provides social assistance in the form of cash to beneficiary families (KPM) who have been designated as program participants, in this case homeless people are included in the criteria for people who are entitled to receive assistance from this program. The aim of PKH is to realize an increase in human resources, as well as change the views and behavior of underprivileged families so that it is easier to obtain health and educational service facilities so that in the future they can move from an underprivileged society to a prosperous society.

PKH provides cash assistance to KPM with terms and conditions determined based on the Integrated Database. PKH participants are required to be registered and present at the nearest health and education facility. From a welfare state perspective, PKH can be considered a protective approach to homelessness. PKH aims to reduce and eradicate poverty in society. Poverty is an indicator of the lack of social welfare. Therefore, PKH can help reduce social welfare problems, especially the problem of poverty which continues to increase, by making efforts to accelerate poverty reduction.

C. The Relevance of PKH as an Approach to Dealing with Homelessness in the Context of a Welfare State

From a welfare state perspective, PKH can be considered as one of the social protection approaches carried out by the state to protect people affected by poverty. The welfare state has the responsibility to ensure social welfare for all its citizens, and PKH is one concrete form of this responsibility. PKH has a strategic role in efforts to reduce and eradicate poverty in society. Poverty itself is one proof of the lack of social welfare. By minimizing social welfare problems, especially in terms of poverty which continues to increase, PKH is one of the accelerated efforts in overcoming poverty.

Apart from that, PKH can also help improve the quality of life through access to education. By receiving assistance from PKH, beneficiary families have a greater opportunity to obtain a decent education, thereby improving the quality of human resources, especially homeless people, in the long term. Therefore, continuous efforts are needed to increase the effectiveness of PKH implementation so that this program can provide optimal benefits for people in need.

In the context of a welfare state, PKH can be considered as an instrument or form of social protection carried out by the state to protect people affected by

poverty, in this case homeless people are one of the marginalized groups included in the scope of this program. As a welfare state, the state has the responsibility to ensure social welfare for all its citizens. PKH is part of the welfare state's efforts to fulfill this responsibility, with a focus on improving the quality of human resources and access to health and education services.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The welfare state is a concept where the government plays an active role in improving the welfare of its people by regulating economic and social life based on law. Indonesia adopted the concept of a welfare state in the 1945 Constitution. The Family Hope Program (PKH) is a conditional social assistance program implemented by the Indonesian Ministry of Social Affairs to improve community welfare, especially in the fields of education and health. PKH is implemented by providing cash assistance to poor families who meet certain requirements. PKH can be considered a social protection approach to homelessness in the context of a welfare state. This program aims to reduce poverty and improve the quality of life through access to education idkan. However, the effectiveness of PKH implementation is still a matter of debate and efforts need to be made to improve it. PKH has relevance as a social protection approach in the context of a welfare state. This program is a manifestation of the state's responsibility in ensuring social welfare for its people, especially including the homeless or vagrants. PKH also plays a strategic role in reducing poverty and minimizing social welfare problems.

Efforts need to be made to increase the effectiveness of the implementation of the Family Hope Program (PKH). This could involve evaluating the process of providing cash assistance, fulfilling requirements, and improving supervision and coordination between relevant agencies. Apart from that, PKH has the aim of improving the quality of life through access to education. Therefore, concrete steps are needed to ensure that PKH recipient families truly have adequate access to education, such as providing quality educational facilities and meeting the educational needs of children from poor families as well as those who are homeless or homeless. Apart from PKH, there is a need to develop a holistic social protection program in the context of a welfare state. This can include other programs involving the education, health, housing and employment sectors, as well as focusing on improving the quality of life of society as a whole so that the ideal of a welfare state can be realized.

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations so further research needs to be done on this topic "Analysis of the Family of Hope Program in Protecting the Homeless to Create a Welfare State".

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